

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-[4'-(4''-Acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4-(4'-methoxyphenyl-amino)-6-(aryluredo)-s-triazine and 2-[4'-(4''-Acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4,6-bis(arylureido)-s-triazine Derivatives

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A large number of thiazoles¹, s-triazines² and urea derivatives³ have been found to possess various biological activities.

These observations led us to prepare the title s-triazine derivatives (**1a-k**, **2a-k**) as possible antimicrobial agents. The synthesis of these s-triazines has been outlined in Scheme 1.

Cyanuric chlorides and 4-(4''-acetamidophenyl)-2-aminothiazole were condensed in equimolar proportions. The resultant product (A), when reacted with *p*-anisidine followed by reaction with arylurea yielded compounds **1a-k**, while when reacted with arylurea only gave compounds **2a-k** (Table 1). Structures of the compounds were established by elemental and spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian 300 spectrophotometer (200 Hz) using TMS as internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

2-[4'-(4''-Acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (A) : To a stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 0-5°, a solution of 4-(4'-acetamidophenyl)-2-

aminothiazole (2.33 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added and neutral pH was maintained. The stirring was continued at the same temperature for 2 h. The solution was then treated with crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol, (50%), m.p. 283°.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS **1a-k** AND **2a-k***

Compd no.	R'	M.p. °C
1a	H	269
b	2'-CH ₃	256
c	3'-CH ₃	253
d	4'-CH ₃	248
e	4'-OCH ₃	251
f	2'-NO ₂	273
g	3'-NO ₂	259
h	4'-NO ₂	262
i	2'-Cl	270
j	3'-Cl	266
k	4'-Cl	254
2a	H	270
b	2'-CH ₃	172
c	3'-CH ₃	259
d	4'-CH ₃	279
e	4'-OCH ₃	267
f	2'-NO ₂	254
g	3'-NO ₂	190
h	4'-NO ₂	275
i	2'-Cl	273
j	3'-Cl	265
k	4'-Cl	164

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Scheme 1

2-[4'-(4''-Acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4-(4'-methoxyphenylamino)-6-chloro-s-triazine : To a stirred solution of 2-[4'-(4''-acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (A; 3.81, g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°, a solution of *p*-anisidine (1.23 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added dropwise for 0.5 h and neutral pH was maintained. The temperature was then gradually raised to 45° during 2h. The solution was then poured in ice-cold water and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol, (44%), m.p. 264°.

2-[4'-(4''-Acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4-(4'-methoxyphenylamino)-6-(aryluroido)-s-triazine (1a-k). *General procedure* : A mixture of 2-[4'-(4''-acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4-(4'-methoxyphenylamino)-6-chloro-s-triazine (4.68g, 0.01 mol) and arylurea (0.01 mol) in dioxan was refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h. The solution was then treated with crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol (yields 34–69%); ν_{\max} 810–815 (C_3N_3), 1490–1495, 1360 1385 (thiazole C=N), 1580–1590 (sec. amine NH),

1 230–1 235, 1 015–1 020 (C–O–C) and 1 660–1 670 cm^{-1} (C=O).

2-[4'-(4"-Acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4,6-bis(arylureido)-s-triazine (**2a–k**). *General procedure* : A mixture of 2-[4'-(4"-acetamidophenyl)thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (**A**; 3.81 g, 0.01 mol) and arylurea (0.02 mol) in dioxan was refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h. The solution was then treated with crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol (yields 22–59%); ν_{max} 810 (C_3N_3), 1 490–1 500, 1 353–1 360 (thiazole C=N), 1 550–1 555 (sec. amine NH), 1 655–1 660 (C=O); δ (DMSO) 7.10 (1H, ethylenic proton of thiazole), 7.84 (4H, NH of arylurea), 7.09 (1H, NH of NHCOCH_3), 7.3 (1H, NH of thiazole), 2.13 (3H, COCH_3) and 7.75 (12H, ArH).

Antimicrobial screening : Compounds **1a–k** and **2a–k** were screened for antimicrobial activity by employing disc-plate technique⁴ at a concentration of 15 mg/disc and tested against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. pyogenes*, *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Maximum activity was observed in compound **1j** against all the four bacteria (zone of inhibition : 4.0, 3.5, 3.0 and 1.5 mm respectively) which indicates that 3'-chlorophenylureido moiety increases the activity. Compounds **1d** and **1f** were also found to exhibit relatively good activity (zone of inhibition 1.0–3.0 mm). Compounds **2a–k** which are obtained by substitution of 3- and 6- both chlorine atoms of 2-[4'-(4"-acetamidophenyl)-

thiazol-2'-ylamino]-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine by arylureido moieties, showed decreases in the activity in comparison to the activity of the compounds **1a–k**. Compounds **2c**, **2e**, **2j** and **2k** were found ineffective in inhibiting the growth of *S. aureus*; *S. pyogenes*; *S. aureus*; *S. pyogenes*; *K. pneumoniae*; and *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* respectively. The remaining compounds displayed the antimicrobial activity in the range of 0.5–2.0 mm. Thus replacement of *p*-methoxyphenylamino group by arylureido moiety at 4-position of the *s*-triazine ring is not observed advantageous.

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